

KFT - Recommendation 9

KFT - Dive Mission Leader Training Courses according to DGUV Rule 101-023 Section 5

Developed by the German Scientific Diving Commission in cooperation with the
German Social Accident Insurance Institution for the Construction Industry –
Prevention

As of March - 2026

Preamble

According to section 5.1 of DGUV Rule 101-023 “Scientific Diving”, every scientific dive operation must be led by a qualified dive mission leader. This leader must be appointed in writing by the company and has the authority to give instructions to the dive team. A dive mission leader must possess the key qualifications required for the dive operation in terms of professional and social skills and be able to monitor and coordinate the operating conditions, the safe execution of the dive, and the efficient implementation of the scientific task underwater. The dive mission leader must also be able to take all necessary measures and, if necessary, initiate further steps in the event of safety-related incidents.

This document aims to provide a framework for how a dive mission leader can acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. It also serves as a guideline for the organization when formally appointing a dive mission leader.

The focus of KFT Recommendation 09 “KFT - Dive Mission Leader Training Courses in accordance with DGUV Rule 101-023 Section 5” is on the planning, execution and follow-up of diving operations with special consideration of safety, risk management and legal frameworks.

According to DGUV Rule 101-023, the responsibility for appointing a dive mission leader lies primarily with the company. In accordance with Section 13 of DGUV Rule 1 “Principles of Prevention” and DGUV Rule 101-023, Section 5, the company decides whether the necessary qualifications for an operation are present and assumes legal responsibility for the appointment. According to DGUV Rule 101-023, Section 5, the basic competence to act as a dive mission leader is certified by an accredited training centre (DGUV Rule 101-023 - Appendix 3). This certification can be provided, for example, by the training centre applying

for certification as a KFT dive mission leader from the KFT (German Diving Association) or by a formal appointment for an operation by the training centre.

KFT certification as a dive mission leader requires a certain minimum standard. This is outlined in the present KFT Recommendation 09.

Basic requirements for qualification as a “dive mission leader” according to DGUV Rule 101-023

- Only qualified personnel may be appointed to lead scientific dives in accordance with DGUV Rule 101-023 "Scientific Diving". These individuals must hold a valid "Certified Scientific Diver" certificate (DGUV) or the "European Scientific Diver" (ESD) qualification. The required qualification must be verified by suitable documentation (e.g., KFT diving operations management certificate or other training certificates) before appointment as dive mission leader.
- The designated dive mission leader must possess not only sound knowledge of diving medicine, diving physics, and diving equipment, but also, and especially, a thorough understanding of the specific diving conditions of the operation. Additionally, the dive mission leader should have sufficient knowledge of the scientific equipment and procedures used during the operation.
- Every person leading a dive operation must present a valid first aid certificate no more than 24 months old.
- The qualification to lead a dive operation, as defined in DGUV Rule 101-023 "Scientific Diving," is deliberately not tied to a specific number of diving hours. This takes into account the fact that scientific dives vary considerably in complexity depending on the task, operational environment, and organizational framework, and this can result in differing requirements for knowledge, experience, and skills. However, practical experience with scientific dives shows that sufficient and robust qualifications to lead a scientific dive generally require that the individual has been actively involved as a scientific diver for several years, gaining experience under diverse operational conditions and within various diving groups.

Regardless of the qualification process for the dive mission leader – through institutional, in-company training by a training company or through a special course with inter-company certification as a KFT dive mission leader – the dive mission leader should acquire the following key qualifications as part of their training.

Key qualifications and course content for becoming a dive mission leader with subsequent certification “KFT dive mission leader”

Theoretical course content

Tasks and responsibilities of the dive mission leader

The dive mission leader assumes on-site company responsibility for the respective dive operation in accordance with applicable occupational health and safety regulations, in particular the relevant DGUV (German Social Accident Insurance) regulations. They are responsible for the organization, execution, and monitoring of the dive operation and have the authority to issue instructions to all members of the diving group. Their instructions are binding and serve to ensure the safe execution of the operation and the protection of the life and health of all participants.

Their duties include, in particular, responsibility for the occupational health and safety of the diving team. This encompasses ensuring that only suitable, trained, and fit personnel participate and that the equipment used meets applicable safety requirements. A key component is the creation of an operational risk assessment in accordance with Section 5 of the German Occupational Health and Safety Act and Section 3 of DGUV Regulation 1 "Principles of Prevention," taking into account the specific hazards of diving as well as the local and organizational conditions.

Based on this risk assessment, the dive mission leader conducts and documents a briefing for the diving group before the start of the dive. Furthermore, they are responsible for the safe, professional, and efficient execution of the planned scientific tasks. They coordinate the workflows within the diving group, monitor compliance with the established safety measures, and continuously oversee the dive.

In the event of safety-related deviations or unforeseen events, he is obliged to take appropriate measures immediately and is authorized to interrupt or terminate the diving operation at any time if this is necessary for safety reasons.

Rights and responsibilities of the dive mission leader

The dive mission leader is authorized and obligated to order and enforce all measures necessary to ensure the safety and health of the diving group. They possess the necessary authority to give instructions to the members of the diving group and are authorized to interrupt or terminate the dive at any time if safety concerns arise.

Their duties include consistently implementing applicable occupational health and safety regulations, in particular the relevant DGUV rules, adhering to risk assessments, and monitoring the established protective measures. They ensure that only suitable, trained, and fit personnel are deployed, that safety-related deficiencies are rectified immediately, and that identified hazards are documented and reported. At the same time, they are obligated to perform their assigned tasks diligently, responsibly, and within their defined responsibilities.

Rights and obligations of the company.

The company bears overall responsibility for safety and health protection during diving operations. They are obligated to create the organizational, personnel, and material conditions necessary to ensure the safe execution of the work. This includes, in particular, compliance with applicable legal regulations, the Occupational Health and Safety Act, and the relevant DGUV regulations and rules.

The company must appoint a suitable and qualified dive mission leader in writing and grant them the necessary authority. They must ensure that responsibilities and accountabilities are clearly defined and known to all involved. Furthermore, they are obligated to ensure that a reliable and up-to-date risk assessment, in accordance with the requirements of the Occupational Health and Safety Act (Sections 5 and 6), is available for every dive and that, based on this assessment, appropriate training is conducted for the entire diving group before the dive.

The company's other obligations include employing only suitable, trained, and healthy personnel, providing appropriate work and diving equipment, and ensuring its proper condition. They must also ensure that sufficient time, financial resources, and organizational resources are available to meet safety requirements.

The company is entitled to delegate tasks to suitable persons to fulfill their obligations. However, overall responsibility remains with them. They must regularly monitor proper execution and immediately initiate appropriate measures if deficiencies are identified.

Frequently Asked Questions Regarding Liability Law

Liability

Liability includes compliance with all applicable laws, regulations, and safety standards during a diving operation. Violations of occupational safety regulations or improper conduct can have legal consequences. This responsibility lies with both the company and the person in charge of the diving operation, with the latter bearing operational responsibility on site.

What does "authorized to give instructions" mean?

The authority to issue instructions means that the dive mission leader is authorized to give binding instructions to all members of the diving group. These instructions serve the purpose of safety, the proper execution of the dive, and the consistent implementation of the risk assessment. All group members are obligated to follow the instructions, provided they do not violate applicable law.

Taking on company responsibility

Assuming company responsibility means that the dive mission leader on site bears full responsibility for safety, health protection, and the organization of the dive operation. This includes providing suitable resources, implementing the risk assessment, monitoring participants, and having the authority to suspend or terminate the operation at any time in the event of safety risks.

Fundamentals of German and European law

The legal basis for safety and health protection during diving operations in Germany is German occupational safety law, in particular the Occupational Safety and Health Act (ArbSchG) and the underlying state regulations (e.g., the Industrial Safety Ordinance (BetrSichV)), as well as the relevant DGUV regulations and rules. These govern the duties and rights of companies and dive mission leader, the preparation of risk assessments, the implementation of training, the deployment of qualified personnel, and the provision of safe work equipment.

At the European level, EU Framework Directive 89/391/EEC (the "Occupational Safety and Health Framework Directive") and other specific directives on occupational safety and health are particularly relevant. These directives oblige member states to enact national laws and regulations that ensure minimum standards for safety and health at work.

National regulations, such as the Occupational Health and Safety Act (ArbSchG), transpose these EU requirements into German law. For diving operations – especially with international diving groups – this means that both the company responsibility and the authority of the dive mission leader to issue instructions must always be within the legal framework of the persons involved and national laws in order to avoid civil and criminal consequences, particularly in cases of negligence, accidents, or disregard for the risk assessment.

Selection and composition of the diving group.

The diving team is assembled in such a way that all participants meet the specific requirements of the operation. Particular attention is paid to professional qualifications, diving experience, medical fitness, and familiarity with the planned work and safety procedures.

The dive mission leader ensures that the group is sufficiently diverse to carry out the scientific tasks efficiently and safely, and that the team size complies with organizational and safety requirements. Before the dive begins, each person must have received instruction and been familiarized with the risk assessment.

The composition of the diving group can be adjusted as needed, should safety considerations, operational conditions, or special tasks require it. All members of the diving group are obligated to follow the instructions of the dive mission leader.

DGUV Rule 101-023 “Scientific Diving”

DGUV Rule 101-023 "Scientific Diving" is the central technical regulation for all activities with scientific objectives underwater. It provides binding guidelines for risk assessment, the qualification of those involved, dive planning and execution, and the responsibilities of the dive management team. It thus forms the basis for safe and responsible scientific diving in Germany.

As part of the training to become a dive mission leader, the purpose and scope of the following laws, regulations and rules are taught in particular with regard to the tasks and duties of the operations manager:

- DGUV Rule 101-023 “Scientific Diving”
- Occupational Health and Safety Act
- Industrial Safety Ordinance
- Regulation on occupational health care (ArbMedVV)
- DGUV Rule 1 “Principles of Prevention”
- DGUV Rule 2 “Company doctors and occupational safety specialists”

Creating risk assessments for scientific diving operations

The dive mission leader is responsible for conducting a complete and thorough risk assessment before every scientific diving expedition. This assessment serves to systematically identify and evaluate all relevant risks and to define the appropriate protective measures. A comprehensive risk assessment with the three components (1) identifying and describing hazards, (2) defining and implementing protective measures, and (3) monitoring implementation and making changes as necessary, takes into account, in particular:

- The operating environment (water depth, current, visibility, temperature, underwater structure)
- The equipment used (diving equipment, breathing gases, measuring instruments)
- the qualifications and physical fitness of the participants
- The specific tasks and activities (e.g. sampling, surveying, handling sensitive organisms) if these concern safety-relevant areas
- The establishment of emergency and rescue measures, including communication and alarm plans

Based on the risk assessment, the dive mission leader conducts the training of the diving group, conveys the applicable safety rules and implements measures to prevent accidents and health damage.

A correctly prepared risk assessment is legally required and forms the basis for the safe execution of scientific dives in accordance with the requirements of the DGUV, in particular the DGUV Rule 101-023 “Scientific Diving”.

Creating and conducting training sessions for scientific diving missions

The dive mission leader conducts the diving group's briefings based on the risk assessment. The goal is to ensure that all participants are fully, understandably, and practically informed about the planned operation.

The instruction includes in particular:

- Explanation of the security and organizational measures taken
- Explanation of the equipment and scientific instruments used, with a focus on their proper use and handling
- Raising awareness of particular hazards and difficult conditions at the scene of the incident
- Procedures in case of emergencies, accidents or unexpected disturbances during the dive

The instruction ensures that the diving group acts safely, responsibly, and in a coordinated manner, and that the risk assessment is consistently implemented. The instruction must be documented in writing in accordance with Section 4 of DGUV Rule1 "Principles of Prevention".

Assessment of diving conditions - even in previously unknown waters

The dive mission leader is responsible for reliably assessing diving and operational conditions, even in previously unfamiliar waters. This includes, in particular, evaluating water and environmental conditions such as water temperature, visibility, health risks from contaminated water, weather, possible diving depth and duration, as well as holding and decompression times.

Assessing operational conditions also includes evaluating tides, currents, shipping traffic, underwater obstacles, and other local features. Particular emphasis is placed on identifying additional hazards and difficulties, as well as deriving appropriate protective and safety measures, the implementation of which must be monitored during the operation.

The dive leader makes independent, reliable, and transparent decisions regarding the termination of a dive operation if problems, safety risks, or health hazards arise. They clarify the applicable regulations and restrictions at the dive site, contact the relevant authorities if necessary, and ensure that the operation is conducted in accordance with legal requirements.

Furthermore, the dive mission leader is responsible for the operational readiness of the safety diver, including during repetitive dives, and plans the dives in such a way that the

safety diver can safely carry out rescue operations in an emergency in accordance with the requirements of DGUV Rule 101-023 and the associated tables.

Acting as a competent first aider and initiating all necessary measures, including triggering the rescue chain.

The dive mission leader is obligated and qualified under the German Criminal Code (StGB) to act immediately and competently in emergencies. This includes recognizing and assessing emergency situations underwater or at the scene, as well as responsibly initiating all necessary first aid measures, including resuscitation, stabilization of the injured, and treatment of medical emergencies.

The dive mission leader initiates the rescue chain, i.e., alerts rescue services, and, if necessary, coordinates the transport of the injured person(s) to the responsible authorities. They ensure that all measures are carried out in accordance with state and professional association regulations and rules, particularly those concerning rescue and recovery in diving accidents.

Furthermore, they are able to initiate advanced measures in cases of decompression sickness, including the necessary hyperbaric chamber treatment in accordance with DGUV Rule 101-023, Section 7. The dive mission leader bears primary responsibility for ensuring the safety of the diving group at all times and for acting efficiently, safely, and in accordance with regulations in the event of accidents or medical emergencies.

Documentation during scientific diving operations

The dive mission leader is responsible for complete, traceable, and proper documentation of all relevant aspects of a scientific diving operation. This documentation serves to ensure occupational safety, accountability, and the quality of scientific results.

The essential contents of the documentation include, in particular, the risk assessment and the instruction of the diving group, including proof that both were carried out correctly. Furthermore, all divers involved must be recorded with their qualifications, medical fitness, and roles assumed (e.g., safety diver).

As part of the operational planning, the dive plan and operational conditions must be documented in writing, including dive time, dive depth, equipment used, water temperature, currents, visibility, special hazards, and any required safety and decompression stops. The course of the operation must also be documented, including any special events, deviations from the dive plan or instructions, safety-related incidents, emergencies, or special scientific observations.

The debriefing must include all findings for improving safety as well as suggestions for future operations. This documentation must be maintained in a way that is comprehensible to third parties and serves as binding evidence in the event of accident investigations, insurance

claims, or official inspections. At the same time, it supports the continuous optimization of safety standards for scientific dives.

Practical content of the training course for diving mission leaders

A key component of the training is the safe and efficient planning and execution of scientific diving operations. To learn these complex tasks in a practical way, participants practice leading diving groups, conducting training sessions, and identifying and overcoming challenges based on real or simulated diving operations.

It is recommended to practice the skills on at least two different diving missions:

- A complex, theoretical diving exercise serves to impart and apply theoretical knowledge.
- A real diving operation allows these skills to be implemented under practical conditions with a diving group on site.

In addition, each participant should conduct a rescue exercise in the role of dive mission leader.

Theoretical diving operation (simulation)

- Eight weeks before the course begins, each participant submits three proposals for complex diving operations from their own experience to the training centre. The training centre selects one operation and notifies the participant four weeks before the course starts. The participants' task is to create a written dive plan, including a complete risk assessment, and to conduct a briefing for a fictitious diving group (approximately 30 minutes per presentation).
- The group discusses the risk assessment and the instructions for the participants.

Real diving operation

- Alongside the theoretical instruction, each participant will complete a real scientific dive, which will be carried out practically as part of the course. The dive mission leader is responsible for creating a complete dive plan, including a risk assessment. In consultation with the training centre, the participants will obtain all necessary information, documents, and permits and conduct the dive on-site with their assigned diving group during the practical portion of the course.

Rescue exercise

- Each participant receives a predefined emergency scenario from the training centre and outlines possible courses of action, explaining the rationale behind their chosen approach. The training centre selects one or two emergency scenarios per diving group, which are then led by the designated dive leader. After the exercise, the scenario is discussed within the group, weaknesses are identified, and potential improvements are explored.

Completion of the training course

The practical examination is supplemented by a documented competency assessment. This takes place within the framework and scope of:

- A joint final colloquium, in which open questions, experiences from the training exercises and theoretical content are brought together.
- A documented written or oral final examination on the above-mentioned theoretical topics.

Exam content

Performance will be evaluated according to the following criteria:

- Careful planning of operations
- Completeness of the risk assessment and instruction before each dive
- Clear and safe operational briefing with the divers
- Ability to safely carry out an operation
- Competent action in a simulated diving accident
- Overall assessment of leadership performance

Time frame

As a guideline for the duration of dive mission leader training, a block course, as offered by some training centres, can be used as a simplified example. Other providers conduct dive mission leader training alongside regular work; however, the overall time commitment should be comparable.

Regardless of whether the training is conducted as a block course or alongside on-the-job training, all participants should complete at least the equivalent of one to two full days of practical training in the role of dive mission leader (TEL). These practical components typically involve multiple dives at different dive sites and should also include varying water depths, potentially repeat dives, and varying operational conditions.

In addition to practical exercises, two to three days of theory sessions should be scheduled. These will cover, in particular, the tasks, responsibilities, and duties of the dive mission leader, the duties of the company, the preparation of risk assessments, and the conduct of training sessions.

In total, the above-mentioned teaching scope results in a time equivalent of four to five days for a group of four to six people, during which numerous exercises are carried out in the group, repeated in different roles, and jointly evaluated and discussed.

Certification

Based on successful participation and passing the examination, the training centre will certify the participant's qualification as a dive mission leader. Based on this certificate, the training centre can apply for the participant to receive the "KFT Dive Mission Leader" certificate. The qualification certificate included in the KFT application form must be signed by the responsible training centre and submitted with the application, along with a description of the training format.